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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AJMAL SHAHZAD bearing USN 6SU19MI001 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADARSH KUMAR K Sbearing USN 6SU19MI002has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AJNAS C Hbearing USN 6SU19MI003has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALAN EMMANUEL JOSHY bearing USN 6SU19MI004 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEX BABU bearing USN 6SU19MI005 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASLAM A Kbearing USN 6SU19MI006 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BADHARIYA Bbearing USN 6SU19MI007has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BHARATH SHIRESHI bearing USN 6SU19MI008 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BILAL ALLAJ bearing USN 6SU19MI009 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATHU SAHANA Nbearing USN 6SU19MI010 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMATHUL RUSFIDA C Hbearing USN 6SU19MI011 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms IBRAHIM KHALEEL bearing USN 6SU19MI012 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LUKMAN K Kbearing USN 6SU19MI013 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEENAKSHY M Kbearing USN 6SU19MI014has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUBEEN Kbearing USN 6SU19MI015 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ASIF K Pbearing USN 6SU19MI016has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED JUNAID bearing USN 6SU19MI017 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED YASEEN K Mbearing USN 6SU19MI018 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NASIF K Pbearing USN 6SU19MI019 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIGIL SURESH MATHEW bearing USN 6SU19MI020 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RASMINA P Pbearing USN 6SU19MI021has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFIYATH NUHA bearing USN 6SU19MI022 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAYOOJ V V bearing USN 6SU19MI023 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHERIN CHRISTI Pbearing USN 6SU19MI024has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms UMAIR YOUSUF bearing USN 6SU19MI025 has completed his/her internship at Father Muller Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20

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